

Editorial

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As I write this, the current climate hardly gives one much cause for optimism. Beyond international events, the situation facing musicians, academic and/or practicing is fairly dire. Arts organisations are facing ever-growing cuts, and most recently Cardiff University has announced that they intend to axe their entire music department. This latest blow to musical academia in the UK is felt especially keenly, as it demonstrates how little the subject is actually understood with the Vice-Chancellor, Professor Wendy Larnar, stating as tacit justification for the cuts that ‘there are two music schools in Cardiff’ and that ‘in a context where resources are so constrained, the sector cannot afford to compete in the way it has historically.’ In the first instance, that the difference between a university department and a conservatoire is clearly not understood is worrying in itself. However, I find myself most disturbed by the latter point.

I would hope that the largest degree of the readers here would agree that we are forever striving to open our performances or research to as wide an audience as possible, such that it might affect the greatest change. We thrive on our ability to work with others; music is inherently collaborative, and I would argue (especially when we discuss Early Music) that it is also inherently interdisciplinary. Thus, I believe that to define an argument for the closing of any music department (especially one consistently rated highly in all UK rankings) on the prevalence of competition is something of a fallacy. Whilst the quality of tertiary education must be ensured, the arts in general need more funding, not less. Moreso than this, to call it competition is perhaps the wrong way of looking at it altogether: variety is important, and we should strive to bring down barriers to wider engagement. Our field is vast (even within the realms of Early Music), and we must ensure that it can be explored by anyone who is interested, for as long as sound learning flourishes.

In July last year, I was particularly fortunate to be a co-organiser of a conference in London, titled *Music & Majesty* (two of the pieces to in the issue to follow stem from this event, so may this serve as an adequate declaration of my own interests). This event represented—I believe—the very best of what modern research and practice into Early Music can represent. Those speaking represented a truly diverse field, as well as branching into adjoining disciplines of history, architecture, art history, and more. As a part of the proceedings, we were able to conduct a service in HM Chapel Royal, St James’s Palace – lending a tangible practical element to the two-day event. I feel privileged to have been a part of it and strive to promote further like activities in order to emphasise how the interplay of several fantastic institutions across the country (purely academic or otherwise). More recently, the Gibbons 400 celebrations in Oxford proved to be a resounding success, further proving the interest that these endeavours can generate; a report/reflection on these events will follow in the next issue.

We must also remember to consider the field beyond just the UK. As this issue of the journal demonstrates, there is much literature beyond the medium of English which is well worth consideration. Giulia Tettamanti’s article, translated from her doctoral work written in

Portuguese, is an exceptional dive into the literature surrounding Silvestro Ganassi, and serves to compound the fact that we are not only part of a national community of musicians, but indeed an international one too.

The content in the issue which follows paints a far more optimistic view of our field than we must often confront. As we proceed, I hope to prolong this thread, capitalising on the collaborative and interdisciplinary spirit of music. There are some big plans ahead, as we continue to raise the profile of the journal to ensure that we can affect the greatest change possible through the work of our contributors. With the above, I know I have been preaching to the choir (or consort, depending on your instrumental persuasion), but I hope we can rely on your continued support as we move along that path.

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